

STUDY ON IN-SITU SYNTHESIZED TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

D. Zhang, W. J. Lu, T. X. Fan, Z. Q. Li, R. J. Wu, G. D. Zhang

State Key Laboratory of Metal Matrix Composites, Shanghai Jiao Tong University,
Shanghai 200030, P. R. China

SUMMARY: In the paper, study on *in situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites at the State Key Laboratory of Metal Matrix Composites (China) is summarized and reviewed. Titanium matrix composites were fabricated via common casting and hot-forging technology utilizing the chemical reaction between titanium and B₄C, graphite. The microstructures were characterized by means of scanning electron microscopy, transmission electron microscope, high-resolution transmission electron microscope. *In situ* synthesized reinforcements are distributed uniformly in matrix alloy. TiB grows in whisker shape due to its B27 crystal structure. TiC grows in dendritic and particle shape. The interfaces between reinforcements and matrix alloy are very clean. There is no any interfacial reaction. The mechanical properties at room temperature and elevated temperature improved with the addition of TiB whiskers and TiC particles although some reduction in ductility was observed. The (TiB_w+TiC_p)/Ti6242 composites with TiB: TiC=1:1 show higher tensile strength, creep rupture life and ductility.

KEYWORDS: titanium matrix composites, *in situ* formation, mechanical properties, microstructure, TiB, TiC.

1. INTRODUCTION

The incorporation of low density, high modulus and high strength reinforcements into titanium, which by itself possesses a high specific strength at room and moderately elevated temperatures, significantly improves its specific modulus, specific strength and creep resistance. The titanium matrix composites (TMCs) reinforced with whisker or particle are conventionally prepared by powder technology [1,2] or liquid metallurgy [3,4], where the ceramic particles are directly incorporated into solid and liquid matrices, respectively. However, titanium matrix composites reinforced with ceramic particles formed *in situ* are an emerging group of discontinuously reinforced composites that have distinct advantages over the conventional TMCs. This process eliminates the interface incompatibility between matrix and reinforcement by creating more thermodynamically stable reinforcements based on their nucleation and growth from parent matrix phase. Thus composites via *in situ* technique demonstrate high specific strength and modulus, as well as excellent oxidation and creep resistance. Self-propagation high-temperature synthesis (SHS) [5,6], mechanical alloying [7], powder metallurgy [8,9,10,11] and rapid solidification processing [12,13] have been used to produce TMCs by *in situ* technique. Among the several techniques avail to synthesize TMCs,

the solidification processes where the reinforcing particles are formed *in situ* in the molten titanium prior to or during its solidification are attractive due to their simplicity, economy and flexibility.

In this paper, we highlight a novel *in situ* process in which traditional ingot metallurgy plus SHS technique were used to produce (TiB+TiC)/Ti composites. Microstructure and tensile properties at room temperature and elevated temperature of *in situ* synthesized (TiB+TiC)/Ti6242 have been discussed detailly.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

For preparing (TiB+TiC)/Ti composites, the raw materials used were two grade sponge titanium, B₄C powder (98%, average particle size: 5~10 μ m), aluminium (98%), silicon (99%), zirconium (98.5%) and master alloy of other alloying elements such as Ti-Sn, Ti-Mo. The design alloy composition is Ti-6Al-2Sn-4Zr-2Mo-0.2Si. The volume percentage of reinforcements is 8%. For the titanium matrix composites with TiB:TiC=1:1, the volume percentage of TiB and TiC are 4.2% and 3.8%, respectively. For the titanium matrix composites with TiB:TiC=4:1, the volume percentage of TiB and TiC are 6.5% and 1.5%, respectively. The stoichiometric ratio of sponge titanium, B₄C powder was blended thoroughly, then they were compacted into pellets. The various amounts of pellets along with the sponge titanium and aluminium, silicon, zirconium, Ti-Sn and Ti-Mo were melted homogeneously in a consumable vacuum arc remelting (VAR) furnace. In order to ensure the chemical homogeneity of the composites, the ingots were melted at least three times. The diameter of the ingots is 100mm. After casting, the ingots were hot-forged into a rod of 20mm diameter. The total reduction of hot-forging, i.e. A_0/A_i , was 25, where A_0 is the cross section area before hot-forging and A_i is the cross section area after hot-forging. The cast samples for microstructure analysis were fabricated in a non-consumable vacuum arc remelting furnace.

Samples for scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were taken from the TMCs. Then the samples were prepared using conventional techniques of grinding and mechanical polishing. Lastly, the samples were etched in Kroll's reagent. The microstructures were characterized by SEM. The character of reinforcements and finer details of composite microstructure were carried out using transmission electron microscope (TEM) and high resolution transmission electron microscope (HREM). Phase identification of the composite was performed using a X-ray diffractometer.

To study the mechanical properties of composites at ambient temperature under tensile loading, samples of 6 mm gauge diameter and 50 mm length were machined from hot-forging rods with the specimen axis parallel to the hot-forging direction. Three specimens were tested using MTS-810 materials testing machine. The strain rate was 10^{-2}s^{-1} . Load-elongation curves were obtained on an X-Y plotting table that was linked to the load cell of the machine and to an extensometer clamped to test samples. The Young's module were determined by measuring the slope of the true stress-true strain curve in the elastic range. Creep testing was conducted in air using a floor-mode Mayes ESM100 testing machine.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 XRD analysis

Figure 1 shows X-ray diffraction patterns for cast samples. They all indicate that the phases in the composites are titanium (hcp), TiB (B27, FeB type) and TiC (B1, NaCl type).

The XRD results show that titanium matrix composites reinforced with different mole ratios of TiB and TiC can be synthesized by the common casting utilizing the chemical reaction between titanium and C, B₄C. The addition of alloying element *i.e.* aluminium did not form other phases when the composition of aluminium is equal to or less than 8 mass%. Compared with different compositions, there are no significant differences in the X-ray diffraction patterns except that there is a difference in the peak intensities of reinforcements. It is clear that the addition of graphite increases the quantity of TiC, *i.e.*, the peak intensity of TiC increases with the addition of graphite. At the same time, the peak intensity of TiB and TiC increases when the volume percent increases from 10 to 20%.

Fig.1: X-ray diffraction patterns of in situ synthesized (TiB+TiC)/Ti composites (a) 10vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti (TiB:TiC=4:1), (b) 10vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti-8wtAl% (TiB:TiC=1:1)

3.2 Microstructure

The microstructures of titanium matrix composites are shown in Fig.2. It shows that the TiB and TiC reinforcements are distributed uniformly in the titanium alloy matrix. These reinforcements are on a large scale ranging from less than 1 μ m to over 100 μ m. Moreover, the reinforcement's morphologies mainly exhibits following shapes: short-fiber shape, dendritic shape and near-equiaxed shape. The results of energy dispersion X-ray spectrometer (EDS) show that the reinforcements with short-fiber shape are TiB whereas the reinforcements with dendritic shape and equiaxed shape are TiC. Compared with sample 1, sample 3 and sample 5, it can be seen that the TiB in sample 3 grows into a coarser short-fiber shape whereas the primary TiC in sample 5 grows into coarser dendritic shape. The coarser TiB reinforcements are a product of unconstrained (primary) growth from the melt, prior to nucleation of the metallic phase. The smaller TiB reinforcements often appear in eutectic-like packets suggestive of coupled growth with the matrix. The coarser TiC reinforcements with dendritic shape are also a product of unconstrained (primary) growth from the melt. The smaller TiC reinforcements are formed during binary and ternary eutectic reaction. It can be seen from Figs.2(e) and (f) that TiC is liable to grow in equiaxed shape due to the addition of aluminium. Compared with sample 1 and sample 2, we can see that the addition of aluminium makes reinforcements to grow in more fine shape. The growth mechanisms of reinforcements are related to their crystal structure and solidification paths. As discussed in paper,¹⁸⁾ TiB grows in short-fiber shape due to its B27 crystal structure whereas TiC grows in dendritic shape and near-equiaxed shape due to its B1 crystal structure.

In order to reveal the structural details of TiB formed in the solidification process, the microstructures of TiB were characterized using TEM and HREM. Fig.3a and Fig.3b show typical TEM images of TiB in transverse and longitudinal views. Fig.3c and Fig.3d are selected area diffraction patterns in Fig.3a and Fig.3b, respectively. TEM revealed that TiB whiskers indexed as the orthorhombic structure TiB (B27) with lattice parameters $a=0.612\text{nm}$, $b=0.306\text{nm}$, and $c=0.456\text{nm}$. In all cases, the whisker axis was found to be parallel to the [010] axis of the B27 cell. The matrix is polycrystalline α -Ti resulting from the

solid transformation of the high-temperature β -Ti phase. Analysis of several selected area diffraction patterns of TiB indicated that the crystallographic planes in these TiB whiskers are always of the type (100), (101) and (10T). The cross angle between the planes (100) and (10T) is 126.6° , which is in good agreement with the theoretical value of 126.7° . From the TEM results, it can be concluded that the growth direction of TiB is [010]. It also can be seen from TEM images that the interface between TiB and the titanium matrix alloy is clean, flat and sharp. There is no interfacial reaction.

Fig. 2: SEM micrographs of (TiB+TiC)/Ti composites

(a) 10vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti(TiB:TiC=4:1), (b)10vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti-8wt%Al(TiB:TiC=4:1),
(c) 20vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti(TiB:TiC=4:1), (d) 20vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti-8wt%Al(TiB:TiC=4:1),
(e) 10vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti(TiB:TiC=1:1), (f)10vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti-8wt%Al(TiB:TiC=1:1),

Fig. 3: TEM bright field images of TiB in in situ synthesized Ti-TiB-TiC composites.
 (a) and (b) are transverse and longitudinal views of TiB,
 (c) and (d) are relative SAD of (a) and (b)

From HREM observations, it is easy to determine crystallographic relationships between TiB and the titanium matrix alloy. Fig.4 is an HREM image showing a TiB embedded in the titanium matrix alloy. The lattice images also reveal that TiB exhibits pronounced planes which correspond to the close-packed planes, *i.e.*, TiB(100), TiB(10T) planes. As shown in the image, TiB is precipitated with a definite crystallographic relationship of $[010]_{\text{TiB}}//[11\bar{2}0]_{\text{Ti}}$. The crystallographic relationship include the following parallel crystal planes: $(100)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{1}\bar{1}00)_{\text{Ti}}$, $(001)_{\text{TiB}}// (0002)_{\text{Ti}}$. Fig.5 is another typical HREM image showing a TiB embedded in the titanium matrix alloy. The following crystallographic relationships can be determined from Fig.5: $[001]_{\text{TiB}}//[01\bar{1}0]_{\text{Ti}}$, $(010)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{2}\bar{1}10)_{\text{Ti}}$, $(200)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{0}002)_{\text{Ti}}$. The following crystallographic relationships may exist according to Fig.5: $[001]_{\text{TiB}}//[01\bar{1}0]_{\text{Ti}}$, $(010)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{0}002)_{\text{Ti}}$, $(200)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{2}\bar{1}10)_{\text{Ti}}$. However, considering the fact that TiB is likely to grow along the direction [010] and form a whisker shape, the (010) plane of TiB is normal to the growth direction, so the (010) plane of TiB can't be parallel to the (0002) plane of the titanium matrix alloy. The crystallographic relationships between TiB and the titanium matrix alloy are $[001]_{\text{TiB}}//[01\bar{1}0]_{\text{Ti}}$, $(010)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{2}\bar{1}10)_{\text{Ti}}$, $(200)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{0}002)_{\text{Ti}}$. It also can be observed from HREM images that the interfaces between TiB and the titanium matrix alloy are atomically flat, sharp and free from any interfacial phase. Apparently, TiB is bonded well with the titanium matrix alloy. The formation of the above crystallographic relations between TiB and the titanium matrix alloy is valuable to minimize the lattice strain at the interface. They are also related to the solidification path and the growth mechanisms of the TiB.

3.3 Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of *in situ* synthesized cast titanium matrix composites and titanium matrix alloy are listed in Table 1 (The strengthening ratio, S , is generally defined as the ratio of composite-to-matrix flow stresses at the same strain.). It can be concluded that the incorporation of reinforcements improves the mechanical properties of composites. Moreover, the mechanical properties of composites improve with the increase of reinforcement's content. HRc value of pure titanium alloy can not be detected by HR-150A hardness test because the value is too low. However, compared with Ti-8 mass%Al alloy, the increase of HRc values is evident due to the incorporation of reinforcements. In all, the mechanical properties improved with the incorporation of reinforcements although some reduction in ductility was observed. The strengthening mechanisms result from the following factors: undertaking load of reinforcements, refine of matrix alloy and formation of high-density dislocations.

Fig. 4: HREM image of the TiB/Ti interface in the (TiB+TiC)/Ti composites along [010] zone axis

Fig. 5: HREM image of the TiB/Ti interface in the (TiB+TiC)/Ti composites along [001] zone axis

Table 1: Mechanical properties of as-cast titanium matrix composites

Sample	Matrix alloy	Volume percent (%)	Measured volume percent (%)		Yield strength (MPa)	Strengthening ratio S	Compressive ductility (%)	HRC
			TiB	TiC				
1	Ti	10	7.83	2.04	631	1.35	36.8	25.4
2	Ti-8wt%Al	10	7.79	2.07	1300	1.57	22.6	46.1
3	Ti	20	15.76	4.07	794	1.70	31.1	33.7
4	Ti-8wt%Al	20	15.71	4.05	1460	1.77	17.3	51.4
5	Ti	10	5.11	4.78	688	1.47	32.5	30.5
6	Ti-8wt%Al	10	5.08	4.80	1253	1.52	21.9	45.8
7	Ti	0			467	/	47.6	/
8	Ti-8wt%Al	0			825	/	26.3	25.3

The mechanical properties measured by tensile testing at room temperature and elevated temperature are listed in Table 2 and Table 3. The tensile properties of *in situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites improve obviously compared with matrix alloy. The strengthening mechanisms result from the following factors: undertaking load, refine of grain size, high-density dislocations. The addition of graphite forms more TiC particle and is valuable to improve the mechanical properties of titanium matrix composites. It is related to existing of TiB that result fracture of composites at low level of applied strain. The mechanical properties of titanium matrix composites at elevated temperature are closely related to the temperature. As temperature increases, the yield strength and ultimate strength decrease, plasticity increases. Compared with matrix alloy, the mechanical properties of *in situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites improve obviously. The analysis of fracture surfaces show that crack are formed due to the fracture of reinforcements, while the cracks are likely to nucleate at the ends of short-fibre TiB and propagate to matrix alloy so that composites failure at high temperature. They indicate that undertaking load of reinforcements is valuable to improve the mechanical properties at low temperature. At high temperature, the strengthening effect results from the interaction between reinforcements and dislocations. TiB with short-fibre shape hinders the movement of dislocation and make dislocations be liable to accumulate and entangle at the ends of TiB whiskers, which becomes crack resource and makes titanium matrix composites failure. The creep rupture lives of *in situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites are shown in Figure 6. Compared with the titanium matrix alloy, the creep rupture lives improved obviously due to the incorporation of *in situ* synthesized reinforcements. The creep rupture lives are closely related to temperature and applied stress. As the temperature and applied load increase, the creep rupture life decreases. The addition of graphite is valuable to improve the creep rupture life. Under the condition of temperature and applied stress, the failure of titanium matrix composites results from the crack that forms at the ends of TiB whisker.

Table 2: Mechanical Properties of In Situ Synthesized (TiB+TiC)/Ti Composites and Matrix Alloy

Specimen	E (GPa)	Y.S. (MPa)	U.T.S (MPa)	Elongation (%)	E ^a (GPa)	Y.S. ^a (MPa)	E ^b (GPa)
8Vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti6242(TiB:TiC=1:1)	131.2	1243.7	1329.8	2.74	130.9	1001.9	138.1
8Vol%(TiB+TiC)/Ti6242(TiB:TiC=4:1)	130.5	1160.6	1234.0	1.35	132.7	1050.0	139.0
Ti6242	110	844	914	10.00			
IMI834	119	910	1030	6.00			

where a points the theoretic values which are calculated by micromechanism, while b points the theoretical value calculated using rule of mixtures.

Table 3 Mechanical Properties of In Situ Synthesized (TiB+TiC)/Ti Composites and Ti Alloy at Elevated Temperature

ϵ	600°C		650°C		700°C		
	σ_b (MPa)	δ (%)	σ_b (MPa)	δ (%)	σ_b (MPa)	δ (%)	
8Vol% (TiB+TiC)/Ti6 242(TiB:TiC=4:1)	3.3×10^{-4}	780.9	13.25	639.1	29.98	423.9	31.04
8Vol% (TiB+TiC)/Ti6 242(TiB:TiC=1:1)	3.3×10^{-4}	786.1	10.20	657.4	11.81	564.3	21.09
8Vol% (TiB+TiC)/Ti6 242(TiB:TiC=4:1)	1.1×10^{-3}	827.7	13.86	718.5	24.28	550.1	41.88
IMI834		635	14.5				

Fig. 6: Creep rupture life vs applied stress for the titanium matrix composites at (a) 873K and (b) 923K

4. CONCLUSION

In the present work, the microstructures and mechanical properties of *in situ* synthesized (TiB+TiC)/Ti composites have been studied, the following results were obtained:

- (1) Titanium matrix composites can be produced by common casting technique utilizing the chemical reactions between titanium and B_4C . The reinforcements TiB and TiC are distributed uniformly in the titanium matrix.
- (2) The interface between reinforcements and titanium matrix alloy are very clean. There is no any interfacial reaction. TiB is bonded well with titanium matrix alloy.
- (3) The following crystallographic relationships between TiB and Ti are determined from observed images: $[010]_{TiB} // [11\bar{2}0]_{Ti}$, $(100)_{TiB} // (1\bar{1}00)_{Ti}$, $(001)_{TiB} // (0002)_{Ti}$ and $[001]_{TiB} // [01\bar{1}0]_{Ti}$, $(010)_{TiB} // (\bar{2}110)_{Ti}$, $(200)_{TiB} // (0002)_{Ti}$.
- (4) The incorporation of TiB whiskers and TiC particles improves the mechanical properties at room temperature and elevated temperature. The addition of graphite can form more TiC particle and improve the mechanical properties.

Acknowledgments

We would like to acknowledge a financial support provided by A Foundation for the Author of National Excellent Doctoral Dissertation of P R China under Grant No. 200332, Major Fundamental Research Project of Shanghai Science and Technology Committee under Grant No.04DZ14002, 03ZR14063 and ItoYama Foundation.

REFERENCES

1. **Wanjara P., Yue S., Drew, R. A. L., et al** ,Key Eng. Mater. Vol.127-131, 1997, pp.415-422.
2. **Abkowitz S., Abkowitz S. M.**, Industrial Heating Vol. 60(9), 1993, pp.32-37.
3. **Lin Y., Zee R. H., Chin A.**, Metall. Trans. A Vol. 22, 1991, pp.859-865.
4. **Zee R., Yang C., Lin Y. X., et al** , J. Mater. Sci. Vol. 26, 1991, pp.3853-3861.
5. **Tsang H. T., Chao C. G., Ma C. Y.**, Scripta Metall. Mater. Vol. 37, 1997, pp.1359-1365.
6. **Rangnath S., Vijayakumar M., Subrahmanyam J.**, Mater. Sci. Eng. A Vol. 149, 1992, pp.253-257.
7. **Teruo Takahashi, J.** Japan. Inst. Metals (in Japanese) Vol. 59, 1995, pp.244-250.
8. **Jiang J. Q., Lim T. S., Kim Y. J., et al** , Mater. Sci. Tech. Vol. 12, 1996, pp.362-365.
9. **Fan Z., Niu H. J., Miodownik A. P., et al** , Key Eng. Mater. Vol. 127-131, 1997, pp. 423-430.
10. **Saito T., Takamiya H., furuta T.**, Mater. Sci. Eng. A Vol. 243, 1998, pp.273-278.
11. **Kobayashi M., Funami K., Suzuki S., Ouchi C.**, Mater. Sci. Eng. A Vol. 243, 1998, pp.279-284.
12. **Soboyejo W. O., Lederich R. J., Sastry S. M. L.**, Acta Metall. Mater. Vol. 42, 1994, pp. 2579-2591.
13. **Dubey S., Lederich R. J., Soboyejo W. O.**, Metall. Mater. Trans. A Vol. 28, 1997, pp. 2037-2047.